

. This survey is being conducted by Samuel Madureira Silva, a PhD candidate at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel, working on testicular organoids as an *in vitro* model for the human testis under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Yoni Baert and Prof. Dr. Ellen Goossens.

Despite the increasing relevance of developmental and reproductive toxicology (DART) in chemical toxicity assessment, two important parts of DART are often overlooked or still do not have widely known/accepted *in vitro* models – **gonadal toxicity** and **placental toxicity**. The first relates to both the reproductive function, through gametogenesis, and endocrine disruption, through steroidogenesis and hormone receptor binding. The latter encases placenta and precursor structures, which are important in regulating the passage of substances to the developing foetus, as well as metabolising substances, detoxifying or detoxifying them, and producing hormones.

With this survey, we aim to better understand the industry's current perspective on these two areas of DART, particularly regarding the application of *in vitro* New Approach Methodologies (NAMs).

The survey takes approximately 30 minutes to complete. However, it does not need to be finished at once - only make sure to re-enter the survey with the same device/browser to continue from where it was stopped.

Contact: samuel.madureira.silva@vub.be

Q1. What is the main area of activity in your company?

- Industrial chemicals
- Pharmaceuticals
- Agrochemical products
- Cosmetics
- Contract research organization (CRO) services and/or method development
- Other

Q2. What type of toxicology activities are conducted?

- Mechanistic toxicology (focused on understanding the cellular, molecular, and biochemical mechanisms by which chemicals exert toxic effects)
- Descriptive toxicology (focused on toxicity testing to evaluate hazard for safety evaluation and regulatory requirements)

Q3. Do you agree with the following statements?

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
Gonadal toxicity is an important area of toxicity assessment in the toxicology activities of your company.	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Placental toxicity is an important area of toxicity assessment in the toxicology activities of your company.

Q4. Do you use/recommend using *in vivo* models outside of general toxicology studies to predict **human gonadal toxicity**?

- Not used/recommended
- Yes, regulatory testing
- Yes, mechanistic investigation

Q5. What *in vivo* models do you use/recommend using to predict **human gonadal toxicity**?

- Rodents
- Dog
- Primates
- Other

Q6. What is the source of the *in vivo* models for **gonadal toxicity** assessment?

- In-house developed
- Guidelines
- Literature described
- Other

Q7. What is your level of confidence in the *in vivo* models used to conclude impact/safety in **human gonads**?

- Very high
- High
- Medium
- Low
- No confidence

Q8. What makes you choose/recommend these models to evaluate **human gonadal toxicity**?

- Regulators' demands
- Cost-efficiency
- Best models available for predicting human gonadal toxicity
- In-house expertise
- Mechanistic reasons

Other

Q9. Do you use/recommend using *in vitro* NAMs for **gonadal toxicity** and in which context?

- Not used/recommended
- Yes, regulatory testing
- Yes, mechanistic investigation
- Yes, screening/ranking of candidate chemicals
- Yes, complement/refine the use of *in vivo* models
- Other

Q10. What would make you choose/recommend (more) *in vitro* NAMs to evaluate **human gonadal toxicity**?

- New regulations requiring new, animal-free models
- More financial resources
- Proven better models for predicting human toxicity
- Different in-house expertise
- Other

Q11. What is your view on using *in vitro* NAMs in **gonadal toxicology** for internal decision making?

- Strongly supportive** – *in vitro* NAMs offer faster, ethical, and reliable insights for internal decision-making.
- Context-dependent** – *in vitro* NAMs are suitable at certain stages but should complement traditional methods as these are still essential in internal decision-making.
- Skeptical** – *in vitro* NAMs may not fully replicate physiological systems and lead to loss of opportunities or carry translational risks.
- Other

Q12. How soon do you think *in vitro* NAMs in **gonadal toxicology** will be used for regulatory purposes?

- Should replace all *in vivo* studies **immediately** for regulatory purposes.
- Should cover several facets of *in vivo* studies in the next **five years** for regulatory purposes.
- At least **ten years** are needed to use them broadly for regulatory purposes.
- More than **twenty years** are needed to use them broadly for regulatory purposes.
- Will **never** cover all current *in vivo* data for regulatory purposes.
- Other

Q35. Are you aware of any initiative/consortia tackling NAMs in the context of **gonadal toxicology**?

- Yes (please specify)

Q13. Do you use/recommend using *in vivo* models outside of general toxicology studies to predict **human placental toxicity**?

- Not used/recommended
- Yes, regulatory testing
- Yes, mechanistic investigation

Q14. What *in vivo* models do you use/recommend using to predict **human placental toxicity**?

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q15. What is the source of the *in vivo* models for **placental toxicity** assessment?

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q16. What is your level of confidence in the *in vivo* models used to conclude impact/safety in **human placenta**?

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q17. What makes you choose/recommend these models to evaluate **human placental toxicity**?

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q18. Do you use/recommend using *in vitro* NAMs for **placental toxicity** and in which context?

- Not used/recommended
- Yes, regulatory testing
- Yes, mechanistic investigation
- Yes, screening/ranking of candidate chemicals
- Yes, complement/refine the use of *in vivo* models
- Other

Q19. What would make you choose/recommend (more) *in vitro* NAMs to evaluate **human placental toxicity**?

- New regulations requiring new, animal-free models
- More financial resources
- Proven better models for predicting human toxicity
- Different in-house expertise
- Other

Q20. What is your view on using *in vitro* NAMs in **placental toxicology** for internal decision making?

- Strongly supportive** – *in vitro* NAMs offer faster, ethical, and reliable insights for internal decision-making.
- Context-dependent** – *in vitro* NAMs are suitable at certain stages but should complement traditional methods as these are still essential in internal decision-making.
- Skeptical** – *in vitro* NAMs may not fully replicate physiological systems and lead to loss of opportunities or carry translational risks.
- Other

Q21. How soon do you think *in vitro* NAMs in **placental toxicology** will be used for regulatory purposes?

- Should replace all *in vivo* studies **immediately** for regulatory purposes.
- Should cover several facets of *in vivo* studies in the next **five years** for regulatory purposes.
- At least **ten years** are needed to use them broadly for regulatory purposes.
- More than **twenty years** are needed to use them broadly for regulatory purposes.
- Will **never** cover all current *in vivo* data for regulatory purposes.
- Other

Q34. Are you aware of any initiative/consortia tackling NAMs in the context of **placental toxicology**?

- Yes (please specify)
- No

Intro models. When responding to the next questions, consult the following detailed tables with *in vitro* cellular/tissue assays available for gametogenesis, gonadal steroidogenesis, and placental function studies:

[DART survey - tables.](#)

Q22. Please attribute a personal level of acquaintance (either from using or reviewing data) and a personal level of confidence in safety translation to each model type below regarding **oogenesis**.

	Level of acquaintance			Level of confidence in safety translation		
	High	Medium	Not acquainted	High	Medium	No confidence
2D – Primary cells > Oocytes are cultured in entire plate-attached follicles.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
2D – PSCs > Human iPSCs differentiated into primordial germ cell-like cells (PGCLCs) differentiate into oogonia.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
3D – Organoids/microtissues > To study oogenesis, follicles can be cultured in scaffolds or floating allowing to keep a 3D architecture.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

3D – Tissue cultures >
 Primordial and primary follicles can be studied in tissue fragments. After a few days in culture, developing follicles are extracted from tissue fragments and oogenesis can then be studied.

Microfluidic and multi-organ systems > Mouse ovarian tissue has been used with human endometrium, fallopian tube, ectocervix and liver cultures in a microfluidic platform. Good oocyte maturation was achieved.

Q23. Do you use/have used any of these models? Do you use or are well acquainted with any other *in vitro* model(s) for **oogenesis** study? (Please specify.)

No

Q24. Please attribute a personal level of acquaintance (either from using or reviewing data) and a personal level of confidence in safety translation to each model type below regarding **spermatogenesis**.

	Level of acquaintance			Level of confidence in safety translation		
	High	Medium	Not acquainted	High	Medium	No confidence
2D – Primary cells > Spermatogonial stem cell cultures in 2D are useful in studying spermatogonial stem cell proliferation.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
2D – Cell lines > Mouse cell lines representing different male germ cells are commercially available.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
2D – PSCs > Human iPSCs or embryonic stem cells have been differentiated into haploid germ cell-like cells.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
3D – Organoids/microtissues > Full spermatogenesis was not achieved but meiotic entry has been observed. Spermatid formation in mouse testicular organoids.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
3D – Tissue cultures > Human testicular cultures show the most advanced spermatogenesis (even full for mouse and rat).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Microfluidic and multi-organ systems > Human testicular organoids can be placed in multi-organ chips with other organ models such as the liver. No spermatogenesis has been achieved.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

Q25. Do you use/have used any of these models? Do you use or are well acquainted with any other *in vitro* model(s) for **spermatogenesis** study? (Please specify.)

no

Q36. In which regulatory framework(s) the development of these NAMs would be useful? (You may identify specific ones for different regulatory frameworks.)

de-risking observed toxicities to better understand mechanism, human relevance, and potentially species-specificity

Q26. Please attribute a personal level of acquaintance (either from using or reviewing data) and a personal level of confidence in safety translation to each model type below regarding **ovarian steroidogenesis**.

	Level of acquaintance			Level of confidence in safety translation		
	High	Medium	Not acquainted	High	Medium	No confidence
2D – Primary cells > Human granulosa cells – progesterone and oestradiol competent and responsive to FSH and LH.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
2D – Cell lines > NCI-H295R - human adrenocortical carcinoma cells: express all key enzymes for steroidogenesis and produce progesterone, testosterone and oestrogen.	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2D – Cell lines > KGN, COV434 and HGL5 - human granulosa cells: variable progesterone and oestrogen production and not all steroidogenic enzymes are present.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
2D – PSCs > Human iPSCs differentiated into granulosa-like cells produce oestrogen when stimulated with FSH.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
3D – Organoids/microtissues > Few protocols are available for ovarian organoids. Follicles can also be cultured straight in matrix scaffolds where oestrogen and progesterone have been detected.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
3D – Tissue cultures > Human ovarian tissue cultures have not been assessed regarding progesterone or oestrogen production.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

Microfluidic and multi-organ systems > Mouse ovarian tissue has been used in a microfluidic platform – oestrogen and progesterone production were higher in microfluidic versus static cultures and responded to hCG.

Fish embryo > Whole teleost fish embryos have been observed to synthesise and metabolise steroid hormones.

Q27. Do you use/have used any of these models? Do you use or are well acquainted with any other *in vitro* model(s) for **ovarian steroidogenesis** study? (Please specify.)

No

Q28. Please attribute a personal level of acquaintance (either from using or reviewing data) and a personal level of confidence in safety translation to each model type below regarding **testicular steroidogenesis**.

	Level of acquaintance			Level of confidence in safety translation		
	High	Medium	Not acquainted	High	Medium	No confidence
2D – Primary cells > Human Leydig cells – testosterone competent in first days in culture and responsive to LH/hCG stimulation.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
2D – Cell lines > NCI-H295R - human adrenocortical carcinoma cells: express all key enzymes for steroidogenesis and produce progesterone, testosterone and oestrogen.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
2D – Cell lines > MA-10, BLTK1 and TM3 - mouse Leydig cells: suited for early steps of steroidogenesis, but low testosterone production.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
2D – PSCs > Human iPSCs differentiated into Leydig cell-like cells. Produce testosterone and express several adult Leydig cell markers and steroidogenic enzymes. Not LH responsive.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
3D – Organoids/microtissues > Testosterone competent organoids with variable LH/hCG responsiveness.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
3D – Tissue cultures > Human testicular cultures produce testosterone – prepubertal ones show higher levels over longer periods.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

Microfluidic and multi-organ systems > In a testis-liver multi-organ-chip, testosterone was detected and metabolised by the liver compartment.

Fish embryo > Whole teleost fish embryos have been observed to synthesise and metabolise steroid hormones.

<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

Q29. Do you use/have used any of these models? Do you use or are well acquainted with any other *in vitro* model(s) for **testicular steroidogenesis** study? (Please specify.)

No

Q37. In which regulatory framework(s) the development of these NAMs would be useful? (You may identify specific ones for different regulatory frameworks.)

Q30. Please attribute a personal level of acquaintance (either from using or reviewing data) and a personal level of confidence in safety translation to each model type below regarding **placental function**.

	Level of acquaintance			Level of confidence in safety translation		
	High	Medium	Not acquainted	High	Medium	No confidence
2D – Primary cells > Human trophoblast cells can be isolated from term or early pregnancy placenta.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
2D – Cell lines > Several cell lines available from choriocarcinoma such as BeWo, JEG-3, and JAR.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
2D – PSCs > Trophoblast stem cells can be derived from iPSCs and embryonic stem cell lines and further specify into syncytiotrophoblasts and extravillous trophoblasts.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
3D – Organoids/microtissues > Trophoblast organoids have been derived from first-trimester cytotrophoblasts resulting in highly differentiated <i>in vivo</i> -like trophoblasts with syncytiotrophoblasts and extravillous trophoblasts.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
3D – Tissue cultures > Placenta <i>ex vivo</i> and placenta explants cultures are performed for a few hours to 3 days.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

Microfluidic and multi-organ systems >

Placenta explant cultures in a microfluidic set-up have their lifetime extended. iPSCs-derived trophoblasts cultured in a microfluidic 3D environment show better placental phenotype.

Q31. Do you use/have used any of these models? Do you use or are well acquainted with any other *in vitro* model(s) for **placental function** study? (Please specify.)

No

Q38. In which regulatory framework(s) the development of these NAMs would be useful? (You may identify specific ones for different regulatory frameworks.)